

POLITICAL REVOLUTIONS IN THE MODERN WORLD

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Annotation: The main purpose of this article is the relevance of studying such a political phenomenon as revolution in the modern world, is related to their historical significance and role in the modern politics of various countries. Historically, many states have gone through revolutions in their development or their appearance is associated with revolutions. This article is devoted to revolutions in his decisions, that is, his final conclusions and methods.

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Revolutions are events that clear the path of modernization and make it politically possible. Modernization itself is, first of all, the formation of democratic political and market capitalist structures, i.e. the development of modern society continues in peaceful, non-revolutionary forms. Revolutions in our time are certainly possible. But they occur precisely in outdated, non-modern countries and perform the function inherent in the great revolutions that introduced Western modernity into history - they pave the way for modernization.

The modern revolution is based on two main traditions: historical and sociological.

According to the first, revolution means a radical break in continuity throughout history, a fundamental break, a "cataclysm-achievement". A universal model of the historical process is considered, revolutions determine the qualitative boundaries in this model. A typical example is Karl Marx's ideas about the sequence of socio-economic formations, where "social revolutions" are considered as qualitative leaps in the transition to a higher stage of development.

The second tradition is based on public speeches that use or threaten violence and coercion to power. The emphasis is shifting from universal models and end results to driving forces, mechanisms and alternative scenarios of social processes, tools that people use to create and change history. This concept is typical of theories of social change, which have replaced the theory of development, whose followers deny that history is built on a pre-prepared, permanent pattern or "logic".

In general, based on the analysis of theoretical and methodological aspects of revolutions as a political phenomenon, the following conclusions can be drawn. Revolutions are an actual phenomenon of modern real politics and the subject of research in political theory. What to do in the event of a revolution?

Timely and necessary unification of the various political forces of the target country, demonstrating dissatisfaction with the existing political system, the legitimate government;

Violation of the trust of the leaders of the target country in the rule of law, as well as in the power and ability to protect the state by law enforcement agencies;

And directly destabilize the situation in the target country, cause panic and distrust of the government, stimulate protest sentiments with the involvement of criminal elements to carry out its actual destabilization;

It is usually necessary to organize a change of power through early elections, armed demonstrations or other methods called nonviolent resistance.

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